

UPSCALING MULTI-CROPPING SYSTEM OF MAIZE- *DESMODIUM SPP* WITH VEGETABLES AS A CONSERVATION STRATEGY IN SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

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Abstract

Due to climate variability, soil infertility, and growing demographic pressure, the need for sustainable farming practices is facing small-scale farmers who mostly rely on agricultural produce. To address the challenges of food and nutrition security, modern farming techniques and multi-cropping systems are being adopted to increase food production. Recently, a new adaptation of intercropping maize with *Desmodium spp.* and vegetables has been introduced. Upscaling the multi-cropping system that combines maize (*Zea mays*), *Desmodium spp.*, and vegetables represents a promising and sustainable development strategy that involves crop diversification, increased crop yields, increased soil fertility, improved soil health, and control of pests and diseases in present and future agriculture. Most studies have only focused on intercrops of not more than two crop species, and the upscaling of the Maize-*Desmodium spp.* system with vegetables increases the total plant population of the intercrops, which may result in below- and above-ground competition. Therefore, there is a need to determine the best plant combination in terms of productivity using the land equivalent ratio, soil moisture at different depths using a soil moisture sensor that uses capacitance to measure dielectric permittivity, which is the function of the water content in soil, and nutrient dynamics trends at the beginning, mid, and end of the season. Upscaling Maize-*Desmodium spp.* with a vegetable cropping system has been instrumental in increasing crop yields. *Desmodium spp.*, a type of leguminous fodder, plays a crucial role in this system. It has the unique ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen, thereby enriching the soil with this essential nutrient. In addition, it contributes to increasing the organic matter in the soil, significantly improving carbon sequestration and the uptake of phosphorus through the synergistic interaction of nitrogen. Hence, it offers an effective alternative to the use of inorganic fertilisers, which can be expensive. By covering the ground, *Desmodium spp.* helps in the conservation of soil moisture, reduces soil erosion, and suppresses the growth of Striga weeds. In conclusion, Maize-*Desmodium spp.*, with a vegetable cropping system, offers a promising approach to sustainably improving crop productivity. By integrating crops more efficiently and leveraging the benefits of crop diversity, farmers can enhance agricultural production while also promoting environmental sustainability. This method of farming, with its focus on efficiency and sustainability, is likely to play a crucial role in meeting the food demands of the growing global population.

Keywords: Multi-cropping, UPSCALE project, crop diversification, sustainable agriculture, climate change